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Joint Class and Domain Continual Learning for Decentralized Federated Processes

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ABSTRACT Continual learning (CL) is attracting attention to learn in dynamic and non-stationary environments, typical of many real applications, such as those related to Internet of things (IoT). So far, learning in IoT scenarios has almost exclusively been studied in a centralized fashion, but CL can be used in decentralized settings involving a multitude of nodes to learn, adapt, and generalize from their streams of data, even with limited communication and computation capabilities. In this work, we formulate a joint Class and Domain Continual Learning problem, where local data at the nodes might include multiple classes belonging to different domains. In our solution, we adopt knowledge distillation (KD) to share knowledge extracted from local models trained with the data at each node and to incrementally generate a global model, while preserving privacy and avoiding centralization bottlenecks. Thanks to KD, the learning process can be performed without any prior information about the model architecture, i.e., every local model can be based on different architectures, which can also differ from the global. The learning process is also agnostic to domain and classes' distribution across the nodes. With these features, our distributed learning solution may assist in privacy preservation and save communication resources, which are fundamental challenges in IoT scenarios. Compared against two baseline losses based on state-of-the-art CL solutions and using different datasets (MNIST, USPS, DomainNet), our proposal outperforms different baselines in terms of accuracy, spanning from a gain of 15.9%, up to 95.4%, by limiting catastrophic forgetting.

INDEX TERMS Class incremental, continual learning, decentralized learning, distributed learning, domain incremental, federated learning, knowledge distillation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) has started to be massively used in Internet of Things (IoT) [1] applications to smartly exploit the huge amount of data they generate. In this context, distributed devices sense a portion of the underlying physical system and collect data to build an ML model with the main aim of controlling the environment. Locally sensed data may belong to different domains and may have different classes due to the complexity and dynamicity of the physical system under control. An interesting example is represented by the smart cities and communities (SCC) scenario [2], in which heterogeneous types of sensors (e.g., cameras, radars, LiDAR, air-quality) are deployed across the whole city to automate and improve the efficiency of different activities and utilities, e.g., urban mobility, waste management, energy management, air

quality monitoring. In such scenarios, it is often undesirable, or even unfeasible, to collect and centralize users' data due to privacy constraints or technological limitations.

A possible solution to this problem is represented by Continual Learning (CL) [3], where the ML model is incrementally learned with the experiences from the different distributed devices. Differently from traditional ML, which is not able to deal with sequential learning problems and tends to catastrophic forgetting (CF) what was learned in the past [4], CL aims to design systems that can continuously learn from new data and address new tasks [5]. CL studies sequential learning in dynamic, non-stationary environments and with data arriving in streaming fashion as (possibly infinite) series of experiences presented to the learner sequentially over time. CL can be classified into three categories [6]:

task-incremental learning¹ (Task-IL), Class-IL, and Domain-IL, depending on whether the new experiences contain new tasks, new classes, or different data distributions, respectively. Combinations of these three categories may be experienced in real-life scenarios, as for the IoT applications introduced above. In this work, we focus on the joint class and domain CL (CDCL) problem, where the data may have experiences belonging to different domains and with different classes.

Recently, CL methods have been widely used in smart city development, as analyzed in [7]. IoT sensors in SCC are usually distributed all over the city, as the experiences in CL. Moreover, they might have different degrees of skewness depending on their location or they might be equipped with heterogeneous hardware that generates different resolution, sensitivity, accuracy or precision. Examples of SCC services which can be managed with CL are urban traffic prediction [8], human activity recognition with privacy preservation [9], or fire detection models [10].

Differently from typical CL settings based on a single stream of data, we consider a scenario with spatially distributed nodes learning in parallel a set of local models from their own data. Moreover, we leverage peer-to-peer communication among nodes that can share and merge their local knowledge. The final objective is to federate the local processes and build a global model from the experiences of all the distributed nodes, as for the decentralized federated learning paradigm [11]. Our proposal aims at embracing the advantages of decentralized settings with respect to centralized: avoiding single point of failure of the central server, higher scalability (e.g., a new node added to the scenario is not required to connect with the central server, but only with the nearest node), and simpler architecture. Moreover, as shown in [12] also communication overhead can be reduced. A fair computational comparison between centralized and decentralized federated learning and our solution is challenging still an open issue since it largely depends on each method's specific implementation [12].

In this work, we address the CDCL problem for classification tasks by exploiting knowledge distillation (KD) [13], which allows to implement the sequential learning without access to the data of the previous nodes [14]. This is a key feature in distributed learning scenarios since it facilitates privacy preservation and communication resource savings. Our proposal enables sequential KD from a set of local models trained with the data at each node (teachers) to generate incrementally (e.g., at every node visit) a global (student) model. We follow response-based KD to align the target label predictions between the teacher and the student. This is performed using only the logit vectors of the student and teacher models [15], i.e., their output vectors of the final layer used to feed the softmax function, and thus independently from the internal ML model architecture. In such a way, our solution generates incrementally the global model

¹Continual learning (CL) is also known as incremental learning (IL), in the text we will use them interchangeably.

without having prior information on the classes or domain distributions in the new experiences at the several nodes. Therefore, the global model is to be common for all the domains. These features are particularly important in IoT applications due to the heterogeneity of sensor types, their computational capabilities, and gathered data. We design the scenarios of the paper based on close-to-real IoT frameworks, then we use standard datasets used in the continual learning community to benchmark the results we achieve. In summary, the proposed contributions of the paper are:

- a model for decentralized federated learning systems based on a joint class and domain incremental approach, which iterates across the experiences of all the distributed nodes;
- a method that solves the CDCL problem and generates a global model without any prior information about the internal model architecture at the local nodes, the domain, and the classes' distribution across the nodes;
- performance analysis of the proposed method considering different distributed learning scenarios, along with an analysis of the impact of typical loss functions used in CL.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the state-of-the-art on Class-IL, Domain-IL, and on Knowledge Distillation in CL problems. In Section III, we present the problem settings and our proposal. Numerical results are analyzed in Section IV, moreover a comparison with other baseline solutions is done in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

From our literature review, it emerges that Class-IL and Domain-IL have been mostly studied as separate problems [16], [17]. Other proposed hybrid solutions ([18]–[20]) are only partially covering the CDCL problem studied in this paper. In [18], the authors proposed a Class-IL method based on von Mises-Fisher (vMF) mixture model to learn a domain-aware representation for addressing the general stability-plasticity dilemma [21]. They developed a bi-level balanced memory strategy to mitigate both the inter- and intra-class data imbalance issue. In [19] and [20], the source-trained model has been adapted to the desired target domain in the presence of domain-shift as well as new classes. These works concentrate on Class-IL and domain adaptation, but not on Domain-IL. In fact, the resulting proposed models are robust to domain drifts, but they suffer from CF.

All the above-mentioned works exploit approaches that require data from both the actual and the previous experiences. On the other hand, utilizing KD may avoid such requirements. Indeed, KD has been largely adopted in Class-IL and Task-IL problems to achieve better generalization performance by transferring knowledge from a pre-trained model to a target network as testified by the vivid literature [22]. In [23], the authors introduced a new KD technique called Learning without forgetting (LwF) for Task-IL problems. LwF fosters the output probability distribution of the new task learner

model to approximate the output probability distribution of the old task learner model using a modified cross-entropy loss, adding an output layer for each new task (multi-head solution). However, in distributed and heterogeneous scenarios (e.g., IoT) this approach may not be effective: e.g., when the data distribution in the nodes is unknown or may vary over time. In such case, it is desired to have only one output layer common for all the domains, namely *single-head solution*.

iCaRL [24] is the first proposed method that combines KD with information from previous experiences (memory replay) for Class-IL problems. In [25], the authors adopt response-based KD to extract knowledge from models trained on the new task data, named expert models, for Task-IL problems. Their *Distillation and Retrospection* method distills information on the new tasks with a KD loss from the experts, while avoiding CF with retrospection, i.e., computing a loss on a buffer of samples for each of the previous tasks. The approaches adopted in [24] and [25] need data from the previous node, which may infringe privacy and add communication overhead. In [26], the authors take over a similar approach as in [25] but on Class-IL problems, and using a data-free approach. To avoid CF, KD is applied to the global general model at the end of the previous experience, similarly to [23]. This approach is extended in [27] for CDCL problems, proposing a multi-head solution and obtaining a global model with a different output layer for each experience tailored for every different domain.

Our proposal aims at filling the gap in the literature on solving a CDCL problem with a single-head solution. To do so, we take inspiration from [26], which uses a response-based KD technique with a loss function composed of mean square error (MSE) and a cross-entropy (CE) loss for the class incremental problem. In detail, we formulate a different loss function based on MSE to address the CDCL problem and be able to deal with domain shift in nodes and approximate a global model common for all classes. Moreover, we propose four distributed learning scenarios to evaluate our proposal under different conditions and mimicking real-world distribution shifts.

Finally, we also cite here [11], which surveys different approaches to decentralized federated learning. The authors differentiate between aggregated and continual approaches, depending on whether the nodes receive multiple or a single model per iteration of the sequential learning process, respectively. The paper also details the advantages and drawbacks of each category. In particular, aggregated approaches (e.g., [28]) tend to fall into repetition and overemphasis on learning from past clients, and incur in high communication and computational overhead. Instead, continual approaches (e.g., [29]) may suffer from CF. We highlight that our approach belongs to the continual category and takes the identified issue of CF as the main design principle to be addressed, as detailed in what follows.

III. DECENTRALIZED FEDERATED LEARNING USING CL

FIGURE 1. Example a distributed learning scenario using CL for a generic round r .

A. PROBLEM SETTING

The reference distributed learning scenario is determined by a set of N nodes: $\mathcal{N} = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\}$, which may have access to a set of G experiences (possible infinite) $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_G\}$. An experience is defined as $S_q = \{s_a^q\}$, where each sample s_a^q of the experience is a tuple $s_a^q = (x_a^q, y_a^q)$, with input $x_a^q \in \mathbb{R}^f$ and target labels y_a^q belonging to a set of C classes $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_C\}$, and one of the D different domains $\mathcal{D} = \{d^1, d^2, \dots, d^D\}$. The generic domain d^j is composed of a set of K classes with $K \leq C$.

In this distributed setting, the goal is to learn a global model that accumulates the knowledge from the different nodes. This can be achieved with a CL approach, by visiting the nodes in sequence, passing the trained general model and other relevant data from one node to the next. We refer to one sequential learning step i (i.e., one visit to a node) as one experience S_q . An example scenario is represented in Fig. 1, in which a sequence of nodes federates their local training processes to collaboratively generate the global model. The learning procedure starts with a random initialization of the global model. It is repeated across the whole set \mathcal{S} , which may include multiple experiences per node and, thus, to sequentially visit the set of nodes \mathcal{N} several times, i.e., perform several rounds $r \geq 0$. In detail, each node n_i during the round r is in the sequential learning step $q = i + rN$ and has access to i) the global model from the previous step M_{q-1} , ii) an external memory \mathcal{K}_{q-1} of the past knowledge and iii) the experience data S_q [5]. The node n_i generates an updated global model M_q by minimizing the loss function $\mathcal{L}(M_{q-1}, \mathcal{K}_{q-1}, S_q)$. Then, the node sends (M_q, \mathcal{K}_q) to the next node in the sequence n_{q+1} .

B. JOINT CDCL METHOD

Our approach leverages response-based KD for updating the global general model. This feature removes the need for sharing the past memory \mathcal{K}_{i-1} , thereby protecting privacy and reducing data transfer among nodes.

In particular, each node n_i during the round r is in the sequential learning step $q = i + rN$ and has access to i) the global model from the previous step, M_{q-1} ii) a local model F_q trained on local data only and iii) the experience data S_q .

FIGURE 2. Diagram of the KD process focusing on step $q = i + rN$ of a generic node i at round N .

During the distillation phase, the input of both M_{q-1} and F_q are the samples x_a^q of the experience S_q . It is to be noted that, the external memory \mathcal{K}_{q-1} is not necessary since it is replaced by the global model M_{q-1} . The node n_i distills M_q by minimizing a loss function $\mathcal{L}(M_{q-1}, F_q, S_q)$. Fig. 2 presents a diagram of the KD process.

We propose to evaluate this \mathcal{L} applying mean square error (MSE) on the logits, i.e., the output vector of the final layer of a model, fed by the input samples x_a^q of the experience S_q . In fact, direct logit matching with MSE has been demonstrated to perform better in response-based KD [30], and is calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{MSE}(M_{q-1}, F_q, S_q) = \frac{\sum_{c=1}^C (l_c - p_c)^2}{C} \quad (1)$$

where:

- l : logit vector of the current global model (M_q), and l_c is the logit of class c ;
- p : logit vector computed by averaging the logits of the previous global model M_{q-1} and current local F_q on the classes that have already been visited during the sequential learning. In case a class has not yet been visited, the corresponding logit value is taken from the current local. p_c is the corresponding logit of class c .

Finally, we highlight here that the availability of experience data S_q is not mandatory, since the loss can also be evaluated with external auxiliary data [31]. In this case, we train the global model M_q using data that may not correspond to any target class of the local model F_q and of the previous global model M_{q-1} . Thus, the logits l and p will not reflect the distribution of the target classes, since they have been computed using the auxiliary data distribution.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this Section, we present the experiments and results achieved to test our approach for solving the CDCL problem described in Section III.

We run the experiments on a computer with an AMD Ryzen 7 3700X 8-Core Processor, with a GPU NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti. The results are obtained from experiments based on 5 independent runs. Source code for the proposed

strategies, along with the experiments configuration and the code to reproduce the experiments is available online². Please refer to the repository for extended details about the hyperparameters of the experiments.

A. EVALUATION SCENARIOS

We set up four different scenarios to evaluate our proposal in close-to-real environments. In each scenario, nodes can experience data from different domains to simulate heterogeneous sensors (e.g., RGB cameras and LIDAR) and only one subset of the classes to skew data in space. Every scenario comprises 10 nodes and 2 domains $\{d^1, d^2\}$ sharing the same 10 classes $\{c_1, \dots, c_{10}\}$. We assume that each node has access to samples belonging to 2 classes, and we defined the following couples of classes $CC = \{(c_1, c_2), (c_3, c_4), (c_5, c_6), (c_7, c_8), (c_9, c_{10})\}$. Every scenario is a different combination among classes and domains, as illustrated in Fig. 3 and described in what follows.

In **Scenario 1**, the couples of classes are distributed among the nodes sequentially for each domain and following the order in CC . Thus, the sequential learning process passes entirely through one domain and later across the other. **Scenario 2** is a more general scenario where the distribution of the couples of classes across the nodes is random and, thus, the domains are no longer sequential (i.e., the learning steps may alternate between one domain and the other). In this scenario, the 5 independent runs of the experiments correspond to different orders of the couples of classes in the experiences. Next, **Scenario 3** is based on the same condition of **Scenario 1**, but nodes can be visited multiple times, i.e., each node participates with several experiences. In particular, we conduct experiments where nodes are visited twice (2 rounds r), for a total of 20 experiences. Lastly, **Scenario 1.A** is an extension of **Scenario 1** with more stringent privacy restrictions: we assume that only the local model F_q is available during the training, while the local data S_q is not accessible. An auxiliary dataset is used during the training for computing the loss of the general model. Here, we want to test our approach when i) data cannot be stored (to avoid leakage), ii) data appears only rarely or irregularly, and iii) data is very sensitive. Examples of very sensitive data in SCC might be citizens' personal information (e.g., biometrics) captured by security cameras.

B. DATASETS

We use two different types of image datasets based on handwritten digits and objects. Within each type, we choose different datasets with a high degree of similarity, as examples of data gathered by heterogeneous sensors in real IoT scenarios belonging to diverse domains.

As for the handwritten digits type, we use MNIST [32], USPS [33], and rotated MNIST. We choose four different rotations of MNIST (20°, 40°, 60° and 80°), following the

²<https://anonymous.4open.science/r/Joint-Class-and-Domain-Continual-Learning-for-Decentralized-Federated-Processes-0B2C/README.md>

FIGURE 3. Scenarios evaluated in this work: **Scenario 1** with the classes and domains distributed in order across the nodes, **Scenario 2** with the classes and domains randomly distributed across the nodes, **Scenario 3** as **Scenario 1** with two rounds, **Scenario 1.A** as **Scenario 1** with auxiliary data.

literature for domain generalization proposed by [34], and used in [35], [36].

As object dataset, we use DomainNet [37] to evaluate our proposal for more complex data and models. To map this dataset into our scenarios, we select 10 of the most frequent classes among the 345 categories {0: computer; 1: dumbbell; 2: flamingo; 3: see_saw; 4: snorkel; 5: stairs; 6: streetlight; 7: submarine; 8: suitcase; 9: zigzag} and 2 domains {*clipart*; *real*} among the 6 present in the dataset. Considering the size and the complexity of the DomainNet datasets, we adopt data augmentation in the training phases to improve the accuracy.

Finally, the auxiliary data used in **Scenario 1.A** are i) FashionMNIST [38], Omniglot [39] and Afro-MNIST [40] for handwritten digit type, and ii) the *painting* domain in DomainNet for the object type. FashionMNIST has been chosen due to its similarity with MNIST: it has 10 classes, and the input images have the same size and data format. Omniglot is a dataset of alphabetic letters and thus shares the nature of characters with the handwritten digits. Afro-MNIST contains four Synthetic MNIST-like Datasets for African Numeral Systems: they contains 10 digits as MNIST and USPS, but not in the Hindu-Arabic system, so we select one of the four domains, the Osmanya one. Regarding DomainNet, the *painting* domain is the most similar to the *clipart* and *real*. It is to be noted that, these auxiliary datasets have different classes with respect to the ones visited by the global model (e.g., Omniglot has alphabetic characters, whereas MNIST and USPS have digits). This implies that the data distribution of the classes of the auxiliary data may not correspond to the target ones when performing the distillation of the global model. In particular, in the handwritten digits settings, FashionMNIST has 10 fashion product classes and Omniglot contains 1623 classes of characters; instead, the local and global models are trained with 10 classes of digits. Similarly, *painting* domain contains all the 345 DomainNet classes, instead of the selected 10 ones.

C. RESULTS FOR HANDWRITTEN DIGIT DATASETS

The model architectures adopted for both local and global models for the handwritten digits datasets are based on LeNet-5 [41] with random initialization. The training of the

local models F_q in the nodes of all the scenarios involves 5 epochs with 0.01 as learning rate, a batch size of 32, cross-entropy loss and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimizer. The distillation of the global model M_q within each node includes an early stopping condition with patience = 3, learning rate = 0.01, SGD optimizer, and it uses 1000 iterations with a batch size of 128 for each epoch.

The local models reach almost 99% of accuracy, for MNIST, rotated MNIST, and USPS. The test set of the global model includes all the classes of both the domains involved, considering the torchvision test splits [42].

In Tab. 1 we present the results of our experiments conducted on MNIST and USPS datasets. The column **S** indicates the simulated scenario; **datasets** defines the datasets involved (MNIST indicated as MN and USPS as U); **available datasets** indicates the data used for the distillation in the experience, i.e., the experience local data S_q (exp. data) or an auxiliary dataset; lastly **avg accuracy** and **stdev accuracy** are the average test accuracy of the global model M_q at the end of the training and its standard deviation. Global model accuracy reaches 0.617 in **Scenario 1**, when MNIST is the first domain and USPS the second. Inverting the order of the datasets in the same scenario makes the accuracy decrease by 0.01 (2%). In **Scenario 2**, with randomized order of the couples of classes among the nodes, a similar accuracy is obtained. Consequently, we can conclude that the order in which experiences are processed marginally affects the performance. In **Scenario 3**, the accuracy grows up to 0.641, since the global model has a second chance to learn in the second round what was forgotten during the first. Then, in **Scenario 1.A**, using FashionMNIST or Omniglot as auxiliary data, the accuracy reaches 0.576, and 0.568 with Osmanya, slightly lower performances with respect to previous the scenarios. This is due to the fact that in this experiment the loss for updating the global model is evaluated without the real target classes data distributions. As discussed in Section III-B, in this scenario, during the distillation of the global model M_q we compute the logits l and p using the auxiliary dataset at each node and, thus, the resulting logits do not reflect the data distribution of the experience in the node and used to train the local model F_q . Consequently, this difference in the data

distributions can affect the accuracy of the global model after the distillation from F_q .

Despite this, the gap in the accuracy of performing the learning without the local data is only 7%.

TABLE 1. Average test accuracy and standard deviation on MNIST and USPS datasets based on 5 runs. The column **S** indicates the simulated scenario and available dataset indicates the data available in the experience.

S	datasets	available dataset	avg accuracy	stdev accuracy
1	MN-U	exp. data	0.617	0.025
1	U-MN	exp. data	0.605	0.006
2	MN-U	exp. data	0.600	0.024
3	MN-U	exp. data	0.641	0.026
1.A	MN-U	Fashion	0.576	0.006
1.A	MN-U	Omniglot	0.576	0.019
1.A	MN-U	Afro (Osmanya)	0.568	0.019

In Tab. 2, we present the results of our experiments conducted on standard MNIST and rotated MNIST (Mrot). For lower rotations, the accuracy is higher with respect to Table 1 in all the scenarios. In fact, MNIST and Mrot are more similar to each other, and training the global model is easier with respect to using the USPS as second domain. Indeed, in **Scenario 1** the accuracy with MNIST rotated of 20° as second domain is 0.782, instead it drops at 0.575 for a rotation of 80° . For the same reason, in **Scenario 1.A** using Mrot 60° or 80° as second domain, the accuracy decreases with respect to Table 1 for the three auxiliary datasets considered. In particular, we can notice that the accuracy is lower when using FashionMNIST as auxiliary dataset. This is due to the fact that FashionMNIST contains images of fashion products, instead Omniglot of handwritten digits and, hence, more similar to MNIST/MNISTrot data. When using Osmanya as auxiliary, the lower accuracy with respect to using Omniglot can be attributed to the misleading similarities in the representation of some numbers with the Hindu-Arabic ones. In Osmanya, the graphical representation of several numbers resembles other digits in Hindu-Arabic system, this is the case of 1 with 5, 2 with 3, 4 with 8, 6 with 9, and 9 with 0.

TABLE 2. Average average test accuracy and (standard deviation) on MNIST and MNIST rotated, based on 4 rotations of MNIST reported in the first column. The row **S** indicates the simulated scenario, data the domains involved and the order in the training, and lastly **av. data** indicates the data used for distillation, and **F-MN** is the Fashion MNIST while **Omni** is the Omniglot dataset.

S	1	1	2	3	1.A	1.A	1.A
data	MN Mrot	Mrot MN	MN Mrot	MN Mrot	MN Mrot	MN Mrot	MN Mrot
av. data	-	-	-	-	F-MN	Omni	Afro
20°	0.792 (0.033)	0.789 (0.015)	0.791 (0.026)	0.782 (0.006)	0.609 (0.104)	0.706 (0.025)	0.644 (0.142)
40°	0.698 (0.016)	0.709 (0.036)	0.708 (0.016)	0.750 (0.032)	0.543 (0.098)	0.583 (0.063)	0.504 (0.094)
60°	0.657 (0.101)	0.610 (0.063)	0.571 (0.046)	0.575 (0.017)	0.436 (0.069)	0.473 (0.033)	0.421 (0.069)
80°	0.527 (0.030)	0.510 (0.040)	0.566 (0.118)	0.595 (0.036)	0.399 (0.052)	0.423 (0.057)	0.402 (0.069)

FIGURE 4. MNIST-USPS, Scenario 1, average global test accuracy and standard deviation during the training.

To delve into the details of the sequential learning process proposed in our approach, we show here Fig. 4, which reports the evolution of the average global test accuracy (in blue) during the training and its standard deviation (light-blue) in **Scenario 1**. The x-axis represents the *cumulative epochs*, i.e., the epochs of the local distillation for each sequential experience q of the global model M_q summed up cumulatively. The accuracy is growing during the distillation, with a positive slope across all the cumulative epochs, which demonstrates that the global model is continuously training new classes and new domains without forgetting. It is to be noted that the exposure to the second domain is only marginally increasing the accuracy, which can be due to the fact that the two domains are similar.

Finally, we investigate how our solution behaves from plasticity and stability perspective. Fig. 5 presents the evolution of the accuracy of the general model M_q in **Scenario 1** evaluated separately on the test data of the different sets of classes present in the nodes (i.e., CC defined in Section IV-A), using both MNIST and USPS data. This figure shows the plasticity-stability trade-off achieved by the global model across the sequential learning steps. From plasticity perspective, the proposed solution is able to correctly learn how to classify new classes when they are processed for the first time (e.g., the accuracy in Fig. 5b increases only when visiting the second node containing the classes (c_3, c_4) after 5 cumulative epochs). Regarding stability, the accuracy of a set of classes CC is only marginally affected by the processing of the other classes in the following nodes (it decreases at most 0.2 across the epochs). This implies that the proposed solution can alleviate CF and, thus, preserves the reached accuracy during the whole training.

D. RESULTS FOR DOMAINNET DATASET

Considering the DomainNet datasets, the architecture selected for the local models and the general model is the ResNet18 [43], with random initialization. The local models F_q are trained for 15 epochs and 0.01 of learning rate, a batch size of 32, cross-entropy loss, and SGD optimizer. Each local model reaches on average 0.85 of accuracy with a standard

FIGURE 5. MNIST-USPS Scenario 1. Average test accuracy and standard deviation based on 5 runs, looking at the nodes with the same classes separately during the training. Once the classes are involved in the training, the forgetting is alleviated: the accuracy does not catastrophically decrease.

deviation of 0.06. It is to be noted that, the local accuracy obtained is lower than in the handwritten digits settings, due to the higher complexity of the DomainNet classification problem. As a reference, when training a classifier with the selected 10 classes in a centralized fashion (i.e., all the classes at once), the accuracy reaches 0.506 for the *clipart* and 0.653 for the *real* domains, with the same conditions used for the local models F_q . The distillation of the global model is performed for a maximum of 10 epochs and includes an early stopping condition with patience = 3, 0.01 of learning rate, SGD optimizer, and uses 250 iterations with a batch size of 128. The test set of the global model includes all the classes of both the domains involved, considering the test split proposed in [37].

In Tab. 3, we report the results for all the scenarios (*clipart* domain referred as *clip*), using as auxiliary data in **Scenario 1.A** the whole *painting* domain (*p.-all*) or only the data related to the selected classes (*p.-10*), defined in Section IV-B. Considering **Scenario 1** and **Scenario 2**, we can notice again that they reach a similar accuracy independently from the order of the domains and classes' distribution among the nodes, as also observed in the handwritten digits datasets. Similarly, in **Scenario 3**, the accuracy is slightly higher with respect to the previous two scenarios since the nodes are visited twice. Finally, in **Scenario 1.A**, it is interesting to notice that when using *p.-10* the accuracy of the global model is higher than when using *p.-all*. The global model in the *p.-10* setting is distilled with the same 10 classes used for training the local models. On the other hand, *p.-all* contains 345 classes. This implies that the loss function in Eq. 1 will also be evaluated on the data belonging to the 335 classes that have not been used to train the local models, introducing more noise in the global model distillation process, as detailed in Section IV-B.

TABLE 3. DomainNet scenarios. Average test accuracy and standard deviation based on 5 runs.

S	datasets	available dataset	avg accuracy	stdev accuracy
1	<i>clip-real</i>	exp. data	0.285	0.027
1	<i>real-clip</i>	exp. data	0.292	0.013
2	<i>clip-real</i>	exp. data	0.284	0.008
3	<i>clip-real</i>	exp. data	0.305	0.021
1.A	<i>clip-real</i>	<i>p.-all</i>	0.269	0.015
1.A	<i>clip-real</i>	<i>p.-10</i>	0.278	0.017

FIGURE 6. DomainNet, Scenario 1 with *clipart* and *real* domains, average test accuracy and standard deviation based on 5 runs. Local accuracy 0.8 on average, subsequently global accuracy is low.

We report in Fig. 6 the evolution of the global test accuracy of the general model M_q during the distillation, in **Scenario 1** (having *clipart* and then *real* domains in the training). We can appreciate that the slope is almost linear across the cumulative epochs, which suggests that the general model is able to incrementally learn from the experiences of the two domains without incurring in CF. This can be appreciated by analyzing the stability and plasticity in Fig. 7, where we present the evolution of the average test accuracy (the blue lines) evaluated separately on the test data of the different sets of classes present in the nodes and the respective standard deviation (light-blue), in **Scenario 1**. We can see that the global model M_q does learn from the second domain, as highlighted in Fig. 7b and Fig. 7c for classes {flaming, see_saw} and {snorkel, stairs}, respectively.

V. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

In this Section, we compare the loss function proposed (\mathcal{L}_{MSE}) with two loss functions typically used in KD for CL, specifically \mathcal{L}_{ED} and \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH} . This comparison aims to justify our proposal of selecting \mathcal{L}_{MSE} by providing some insight regarding the behavior of different loss functions in CDCL scenarios. We begin by defining these two benchmark losses and comparing average test accuracy. Then we focus on the \mathcal{L}_{ED} training loss, and reviewing accuracy across experiences in \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH} . Following this, in the second subsection of this Section we introduce the forgetting metric as defined in [44] and provide a comparison based on this measure.

FIGURE 7. DomainNet Scenario 1. Average test accuracy and standard deviation, based on 5 runs, looking at the nodes with the same classes separately during the training.

A. ACCURACY AND LOSS ANALYSIS

The first baseline loss function \mathcal{L}_{ED} is proposed in [26]. \mathcal{L}_{ED} is calculated as $\mathcal{L}_{ED} = \mathcal{L}_{MSE} + \mathcal{L}_{CE}$, where the cross-entropy (\mathcal{L}_{CE}) is added to facilitate learning new classes. \mathcal{L}_{CE} describes how the predicted distribution is close to the true distribution. In particular,

$$\mathcal{L}_{CE} = -p_v \log(l_v) \tag{2}$$

where $v = \arg \max_{c \in C} (p_c)$, and l and p are logit vectors defined as in Eq. 1.

The second baseline loss function \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} is a modified version of the LwF proposal in [23]. In this case, the loss is composed of two terms: $\mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} = MSE + \mathcal{L}_{CE}$. The MSE component is a KD loss used to avoid forgetting and we evaluate it as an MSE loss [30]

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{c=1}^C (l_c - r_c)^2}{C} \tag{3}$$

Note that this MSE loss differs from Eq. 1 since in \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} we follow the paradigm proposed by [23] where the KD is calculated using the current global model (logit l of M_q), and a frozen copy of the previous global model (logit vector r of M_{q-1} , instead of p used in Eq. 1). In fact, MSE in \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} is devoted to only retain the old information, whereas the second term \mathcal{L}_{CE} is the experience loss used to learn from the current experience, evaluated as in Eq. 2.

In Fig. 8, we compare the accuracy of the global model M_q applying \mathcal{L}_{MSE} , \mathcal{L}_{ED} and \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} . \mathcal{L}_{MSE} reaches higher accuracy with respect to both \mathcal{L}_{ED} and \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} in all the reported scenarios. Regarding \mathcal{L}_{ED} , the accuracy increment spans from 7.7% in **Scenario 1** with MNIST-Mrot80°, up to 15.9% in **Scenario 1.A** with MNIST-USPS. Considering \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} , \mathcal{L}_{MSE} enables a higher increment of the accuracy, spanning from 10.9% in **Scenario 1** with MNIST-Mrot80° and 21.3% with clipart-real, to 95.4% in **Scenario 1** with MNIST-Mrot40° and 94.3% in **Scenario 1.A** with MNIST-USPS. In summary, our proposal is able to improve by 15.4% also \mathcal{L}_{ED} , despite the low accuracy experienced in DomainNet, as discussed in Section IV-D.

In Fig. 9 we show the evolution of the two different components (\mathcal{L}_{MSE} and \mathcal{L}_{CE}) of \mathcal{L}_{ED} during the distillation of the global model considering MNIST and USPS. We compare the results using **Scenario 1** since the ordered nodes simplify the analysis, as the order of classes and domains is maintained.

FIGURE 8. Average test accuracy based on 5 runs. Comparison between the loss based on the \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} approach, \mathcal{L}_{ED} and our proposal \mathcal{L}_{MSE} . Our proposal accuracy always outperforms the others.

We can distinguish when a new node is visited by the peaks in the train losses. We report the \mathcal{L}_{CE} training loss and the training \mathcal{L}_{MSE} loss of the global model, in blue and orange, respectively. Moreover, we report the test accuracy with a dashed purple line. We can notice that the \mathcal{L}_{CE} train loss grows faster with respect to the \mathcal{L}_{MSE} as the number of epochs increases. For this reason, at each new node, the gap between the two losses grows. Starting from epoch 25 (when visiting the 6-th node), the \mathcal{L}_{CE} starts becoming two to three times bigger than the \mathcal{L}_{MSE} . Starting from this sequential learning step, the \mathcal{L}_{CE} is decreasing during the distillation of M_q and, thus, the overall loss is decreasing. The difference in amplitude between \mathcal{L}_{CE} and \mathcal{L}_{MSE} train losses makes the effect of \mathcal{L}_{MSE} negligible with respect to the other. Thus, even when \mathcal{L}_{MSE} is growing (e.g., during the 6-th iteration and the last two), the overall loss decreases with \mathcal{L}_{CE} loss, which jeopardizes the KD process. Consequently, in CDCL scenarios the effect of the \mathcal{L}_{CE} loss may negatively impact the KD process. A possible solution for this issue is represented by the introduction of a coefficient to equalize the different amplitudes of the loss components. Such a coefficient should be adapted to the specific dataset. We consider that this investigation is outside the scope of the paper.

In Fig. 10 we consider the global test accuracy of M_q computed on the test data of the classes {0, 1} and {6, 7} during the sequential learning across the nodes in the **Scenario 1** having MNIST and USPS domains, using the \mathcal{L}_{LwF-SH} . The accuracy of the classes {0, 1} reaches 1 only during the first experience where the node contains their data. Subsequently,

FIGURE 9. \mathcal{L}_{ED} training loss, Scenario 1 MNIST-USPS. Corresponding the peaks of the training losses with the beginning of the training of a new node, the \mathcal{L}_{CE} train loss grows in amplitude as more nodes are involved, making the \mathcal{L}_{MSE} loss negligible with respect to the other.

FIGURE 10. MNIST-USPS, Scenario 1, average test nodes accuracy and standard deviation with \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH} , based on 5 runs.

the accuracy drops below 0.4 and returns around 0.8 after 20 epochs, when the data in the experience belong to classes $\{0, 1\}$. Then, the accuracy returns below 0.4 incurring in CF. The accuracy of classes $\{6, 7\}$ reaches 0.4 during the distillation of the experiences with data belonging to those classes, whereas it drops to zero during the other iterations. This means that the model is not able to adapt and suffers CF when using \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH} . Thus, LWF approaches need the specialized output layer to effectively work in CDCL scenarios.

In Fig. 11 we analyze the ability of the models to generalize on unseen domains by evaluating the accuracy of the two domains separately during the sequential learning process. To do so, we focus on Scenario 1, as it suits such type of analysis. We first evaluate the accuracy of both domains with the global model trained with the experiences belonging to the first dataset (namely MNIST or clipart), i.e., at the end of the fourth experience. Then, we evaluate the accuracy of the global model after the entire training process. As expected, results show that our proposal evaluated at the fourth experience has higher test accuracy in the first domain with respect to the second domain, since the experiences with data belonging to the second domain have not been visited yet. Moreover \mathcal{L}_{MSE} has higher accuracy than the other two (\mathcal{L}_{ED} , \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH}). By the end of the training (i.e., after the ninth experience), the accuracy improves using \mathcal{L}_{MSE} in both domains in all the scenarios considered, always outperforming the other two benchmarks in the first domain (in the figure, Experience 9 DOMAIN 1). Considering the second domain (Experience 9 DOMAIN 2), \mathcal{L}_{ED} outperforms \mathcal{L}_{MSE} when considering

FIGURE 11. Accuracy computed in Scenario 1 after the first domain is introduced (i.e. experience n 4) and at the end of the train, divided per domain, for all the pair of domains analyzed.

datasets MNIST-USPS and MNIST-MNIST60°. However, we want to highlight that in the scenario with MNIST-USPS datasets, although \mathcal{L}_{MSE} reaches a lower accuracy (0.40) on the USPS after the fourth experience with respect to \mathcal{L}_{ED} (0.48), it reaches comparable accuracy on USPS by the end of the training (0.48), and improves the accuracy on MNIST (from 0.77 to 0.79). Therefore, despite the higher accuracy reached by \mathcal{L}_{ED} in USPS, the final accuracy of the global model (in Fig. 8) our proposal is highest compared to the benchmark thanks to the higher accuracy in MNIST. Concluding, even if \mathcal{L}_{MSE} does not have always the best generalization capabilities, it presents higher stability in retaining the information (accuracy of the two domains never decreases) and good plasticity, being able to not forget what it learned in the previous experiences as we show in Section V-B.

In this Section, we observed that two commonly used loss functions in CL (\mathcal{L}_{ED} , \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH}) are not able to generalize to the new domain.

This study led us to investigate alternative solutions and inspired the definition of \mathcal{L}_{MSE} .

B. FORGETTING EVALUATION

In this Section, we investigate the ability of retaining information of the evaluated solutions. To do so, we rely on the forgetting of task F_t in CL as defined in [44], with $t \in [2, T]$ given T tasks:

$$F_t = \frac{1}{t-1} \sum_{i=1}^{t-1} (L_i(w_t) - L_i(w_i)). \quad (4)$$

Where $i \in [1, t-1]$ are the old tasks, and $L_i(w_t) - L_i(w_i)$ denotes the performance loss difference between w_i (the result after training task i) and w_t (the result after training task t) on test data of task i . In this paper, the tasks in Eq. 4 are the experiences. In Fig. 12 we present the average of the five runs executed for our solution and the two benchmarks of:

- the forgetting values for each experience as defined above in Eq. 4 - with blue bars (note that in the first and the last experiences is not possible to compute it);
- the experiences test accuracy at the end of the training - with solid orange lines;

FIGURE 12. Forgetting metric and test accuracy per experience in scenario 1 with MNIST-USPS.

- the test accuracy evaluated on the final global model on the whole test datasets - with dark green lines.

We focus on the first scenario, with MNIST-USPS datasets, for the sake of interpretability of the results. \mathcal{L}_{MSE} provides forgetting values similar to or lower than the other two losses, and with less variation. This implies that \mathcal{L}_{ED} is able to retain the knowledge acquired in previous experiences. The models trained with \mathcal{L}_{ED} are clearly more prone to forget the second domain (starting from the fourth experience). The models trained with \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH} , since they have a very low accuracy, present forgetting values that are not meaningful for this analysis. Concluding, \mathcal{L}_{MSE} presents a more balanced behavior from plasticity-stability perspective being able to retain past knowledge and acquire new info.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has investigated decentralized learning in scenarios with spatially distributed data sources. We have proposed to federate the local training processes and build a global general model by distilling knowledge sequentially from the different local data. We have stated the decentralized federated learning as a joint Class and Domain Incremental Continual Learning problem. We have proposed a response-based KD approach with MSE loss function to incrementally train the global model from a stream of pretrained local models. Our solution is demonstrated to provide a flexible and collaborative solution for dynamic and non-stationary environments, such as those of IoT applications. Results show that our solution reaches good accuracy across various scenarios and datasets, by effectively addressing challenges related to CF and domain shifts. Compared to alternative loss functions (\mathcal{L}_{ED} and \mathcal{L}_{LWF-SH}) typically used in CL literature, it achieves higher accuracy in all the reported scenarios, and outperforms them by up to 15.9%, and 95.4%, respectively.

Future work may consider a further generalization of this solution where it does not need to know the classes a priori, i.e., considering a classifier that grows in terms of classes in each new experience. Further exploration and application in real-world settings will be conducted to pursue a more comprehensive understanding of the potential impact of the proposed solution. This may include studies on time series prediction tasks, audio-video prediction or scenarios

involving multimodal datasets. Further studies could explore different data distributions across nodes, such as applying the Dirichlet distribution [45], to convert benchmark centralized dataset to close-to-real distributed data with different levels of skewness. Future work will focus on analyzing energy consumption and exploring potential optimizations, which may include alternative knowledge distillation methods, such as cross-architecture distillation [46] which help to generalize better to different model architectures, if present in the scenario. Feature distillation can also be explored considering learning techniques designed to extract features, such as contrastive learning [47]. Considering the security problem in FL settings, many works have already addressed this problem [48], [49]. When adopting decentralized solutions, future work may consider Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) [50], due to its distributed approach at hardware level that can fit decentralized IoT scenarios. Alternatively, at software level, cryptographic methods can be studied, such as secure multi-party computing (SMC) [51], homomorphic encryption (HE) [52], and zero-knowledge proof (ZKP) [53].

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